

MICROSTRUCTURE - PROPERTY STUDIES IN RHEOCAST SiC_p REINFORCED MMCs BASED ON RECYCLED ALUMINIUM ALLOY MATRICES

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ABSTRACT

Recycled 2024 and 6061 Al alloys have been used as matrices for discontinuously reinforced (5vol%, 15vol%) SiC_p MMCs due to their low cost as compared to primary Al alloys. The alloy matrices and the composites were prepared by rheocasting and squeeze casting. Preliminary studies of the tensile properties of the alloys and MMCs in the squeeze cast condition have shown improvements of the UTS and YS with the addition of SiC_p and no interface reactions. Defects such as clusters of SiC_p , microvoids and non-uniform equiaxed grain size distributions were observed in the composites. Fracture occurred through intermetallic compounds in the unreinforced alloys and the MMCs.

Keywords: Metal Matrix Composites, Recycled aluminium alloys, Rheocasting, Mechanical Properties.

I. INTRODUCTION

Discontinuously reinforced composites can be manufactured at low cost by using traditional casting techniques and cheap reinforcements. They exhibit isotropic behaviour and can be supplied in various forms such as semi-finished products and ingots which can be shaped via squeeze casting or forging and rolling (1,2). These are some of the reasons that Al/ SiC_p MMCs have attracted industrial interest.

Aluminium alloys have been considered as matrices in MMCs due to their low cost, availability and ease of working. For the aluminium industry the recyclability of Al is very important because of the low ratio of the energy required to remelt Al to the energy required for its primary production (1/3-1/4)(3,4). Indeed the price of secondary Al is usually about 20% cheaper than the primary Al and the use of the former in MMCs could be advantageous especially when the material price is the factor determining the use of an Al based MMC.

Rheocasting is one of the many routes currently available for the production of particulate reinforced MMCs (1,5). In rheocasting the addition of the reinforcing particles to the surface of the semi-solid slurry during continuous and vigorous stirring increases the chances of porosity in the material, although this effect can be reduced considerably by squeeze casting the rheocast alloy.

Environmental issues are becoming increasingly important in all areas of industry, the production of MMCs being no exception. To our knowledge no data is available (a) on the processing of MMCs with recycled (scrap) alloys as matrices, (b) on the type and level of impurities that are acceptable in secondary Al in terms of interfacial phenomena and (c) on the properties of such composites.

This paper presents preliminary results from a research programme concerning rheocast MMCs based on recycled 2024 and 6061 alloy matrices reinforced with 5vol% and 15vol% SiC_p of 13µm average size. The paper concentrates on the microstructure of the composites in the as rheocast condition and on their tensile strength.

II. MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The compositions of the 2024 and 6061 alloys used as matrices in the MMCs are given in Table 1.

Alloy	Al	Cu	Zn	Mg	Fe	Mn	Ni	Pb	Sn	Tl	Cr	V	Zr	Si
2024	Balance	4.40	0.008	1.51	0.31	0.49	0.002	0.003	0.008	0.001	0.004	0.10
6061	Balance	0.31	0.009	1.02	0.19	0.09	0.005	0.009	0.004	0.12	0.20	0.005	0.31

Table 1: Composition of alloys (wt%)

The liquidus-solidus ranges of 673-595 °C and 660-579 °C of the 6061 and 2024 alloys respectively were determined by DTA under an argon atmosphere at a heating rate of 10 °C/min. The SiC particles of 13 µm average size were oxidised at 1000 °C for 25h prior to addition in the melt. This treatment gave a 4% increase in SiC_p weight and was carried out in order to minimise the reaction between these particles and the aluminium matrix to produce aluminium carbide (6).

Figure 1: Manufacturing Process

Once the melt temperature had been achieved the SiC particles were added into the vortex formed due to the agitation of the melt, as shown in step 5 in figure 1. The addition temperature was 650 °C and 630 °C for the 6061 and 2024 alloy melts respectively. At these temperatures, the volume fraction solid was 0.63 and 0.46 for the 6061 alloys respectively. Agitation of the melt was continued at the same speed (1000 rpm) for 40 min at which point the slurry was poured and squeeze casting was performed at a pressure of 70 MPa, as shown in steps 6,7 and 8 in figure 1. The mould temperature was 350 °C.

The microstructure of the alloys was studied by optical microscopy and SEM. Tensile tests were carried out on the as cast materials at room temperature in a 6025 INSTRON universal testing machine using cylindrical specimens and according to ASTM D-3552 standard. Four specimens were tested for each material.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The microstructure of the 6061/SiC_p rheocast composite is shown in the figure 2. The matrix equiaxed grains are surrounded by regions containing Al intermetallic compounds identified by EDS as phases containing Al-Si-Mg and Al-Si-Fe-Mn-Cu-Cr in the 6061 alloy and Al-Cu, Al-Cu-Si-Mg and Al-Cu-Si-Mn-Fe in the 2024 alloy (9). The 6061 alloy exhibited a more homogeneous equiaxed grain size distribution than the 2024 alloy. Several large equiaxed grains were observed in the 2024 alloy probably arising from the agglomeration of smaller equiaxed grains during solidification due to the application of an unsuitable cooling rate. Indeed the latter is an important processing parameter as it directly affects the equiaxed grain size distribution which in turn influences the mechanical properties of the composite.

Figure 2: SEM micrograph of a 6061 recycled alloy reinforced with 5% vol of SiC_p(x100).

Figure 3: Microstructure of a 2024 recycled alloy reinforced with 15% vol of SiC_p (x200).

As can be seen in the figure 2, the SiC particles were located almost exclusively at the equiaxed grain boundaries (6) as a result of the rejection of the particles at the solid-liquid interface during solidification. The particle clusters are attributed partly to the rejection of the particles at the solid-liquid interface (6) and partly to the method of their addition in which the particles fall into the slurry as soft agglomerates which are difficult to break in the mixing process. The distribution of the SiC particles appeared to have been improved in the composites with 15 vol% SiC as compared to the 5vol % level of reinforcement (figure 3), and is in agreement with other experimental work (10).

Table 2 indicates the YS, UTS and maximum elongation to failure for the tensile test specimens. For the YS and UTS the average, maximum and minimum values are stated. The tensile strength of the 2024 unreinforced alloy was lower than the UTS of the primary alloy, the latter being in the range 180-200 MPa without any heat treatment. This difference is attributed to the slight differences in the compositions of the alloy used as matrix in our composites and the commercially available alloy (7,8).

MATERIAL	SiC _p V _f (%)	Y.S. (MPa)	Max-Min	UTS(MPa)	Max-Min	Max El(%)
6061	0	75	74-83	136	125-138	4,3
	5	85	82-88	147	138-153	2,5
	15	97	90-99	176	170-186	1,3
2024	0	102	97-106	153	148-159	0,6
	5	112	105-115	176	167-178	0,5
	15	125	119-128	185	183-197	0,4

Table 2: Mechanical Properties of MMCs and rheocast alloys.

For both the studied alloys, increasing the addition of SiC_p can be seen to reduce the maximum elongation to fracture of the resulting composites.

The UTS and YS of the composites in the cast condition were improved with respect to those the alloy matrices. Further improvements are expected after current process optimisation, homogenisation and heat treatment studies are completed.

Fractography of the tensile specimens revealed that fracture had taken place through the intermetallic compounds in the two MMCs and the alloy matrices. In the micrograph shown in figure 4, the compounds are seen as thin white lines. The presence of microvoids (shrinkage) has been observed which together with the presence of particle clusters are expected to have had a direct influence on the value of the tensile properties of the materials.

Figure 4: SEM micrograph showing the intermetallic compounds for the 6061 recycled alloy (x400).

Figure 5: SEM micrograph showing the good adhesion between the matrix and reinforcements for the 6061 recycled alloy reinforced with 15% vol of SiC_p (x1000).

As shown in figure 5, there is good bonding between the SiC particles and the Al matrix. At this stage of our research no compounds have been observed at the interface due presumably to the low level of impurities present in the recycled alloy matrices and the prior oxidising treatment of the SiC_p . However, some cracked particles are visible. This may be a consequence of the mixing process and/or the micromechanisms of fracture of the composite. This phenomenon is currently studied on polished transverse sections in the loading direction of specimens obtained from the middle of the tensile tested specimens.

IV.CONCLUSIONS

- 1.- Recycled 2024 and 6061 Al alloys have been considered as matrices for discontinuously reinforced MMCs due to their low cost compared to primary Al alloys.
- 2.- The alloy matrices and the composites were prepared by rheocasting and squeeze casting, the latter materials at 5vol % and 15vol % SiC_p levels of reinforcement.
- 3.- The tensile properties of the alloys and MMCs in the squeeze cast condition were evaluated and the UTS and YS of the alloy matrices were improved with the addition of SiC_p. However, the maximum elongation to failure was reduced.
- 4.- Defects such as clusters of SiC_p, microvoids and non-uniform equiaxed grain size distributions were observed in the composites.
- 5.- Fracture occurred through intermetallic compounds in the unreinforced alloys and the MMCs.
- 6.- There were no obvious interface reactions in the composites.

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